

Cutaneotrichosporon curvatum and *Yarrowia lipolytica* as key players for green chemistry: efficient oil producers from food waste via the carboxylate platform

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ABSTRACT

Cutaneotrichosporon curvatum and *Yarrowia lipolytica* can accumulate microbial oils using short-chain fatty acids (SCFA) as carbon sources. SCFAs-rich media often contain significant amounts of nitrogen that prevent high carbon:nitrogen (C:N) ratios necessary to boost lipid production. This work assessed the intrinsic ability of *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica* to produce high amounts of microbial oils from these unusual carbon sources. Results demonstrated that minor differences in SCFA concentration (only 2 g/L) had a significant effect on yeast growth and lipid production. A C:N of 80 promoted yeast growth at all SCFA concentrations and favored SCFA consumption at 19 g/L SCFAs. The different SCFA uptake preferences in *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica* highlighted the importance of considering the SCFA profile to select a suitable yeast strain for microbial oils production. At the most challenging SCFA concentration (19 g/L), $57.2\% \pm 1.6\%$ (w/w) and $78.4 \pm 0.6\%$ (w/w) lipid content were obtained in *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica*, respectively. These values are among the highest reported for wild-type strains. To circumvent the challenges associated with media with high nitrogen content, this report also proved struvite precipitation as an effective method for increasing lipid production (from $17.9 \pm 3.9\%$ (w/w) to $41.9 \pm 2.6\%$ (w/w)) after nitrogen removal in food waste-derived media.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Slight variations in SCFA concentrations have a relevant effect on yeast lipid production
- High nitrogen availability is crucial to promote cell growth at very high SCFA concentrations
- C:N effect on cell growth and lipid production is specie-specific and may depend on yeast robustness
- Yeast strains have diverse SCFA preferences and differently metabolize these acids
- Struvite precipitation effectively removes nitrogen from real digestates increasing C:N

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1. Introduction

There is an urgent need to find sustainable routes for producing biofuels and biochemicals to achieve greener chemical industries. In this context, microbial oils have emerged as alternative sources of oleochemicals that can replace non-renewable fuels and chemicals in different industrial sectors

[1]. To attain cost-effective processes and achieve a successful expansion of green biotechnology, it is crucial to use renewable carbon sources for microbial oil production. In this sense, short-chain fatty acids (SCFA) obtained in a shortened anaerobic digestion process of organic residues [2] have been shown to be promising low-cost alternative carbon

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sources for microbial oil production. SCFA are monocarboxylic acids with different carbon chain lengths (C2 to C6). Their concentration and profile in digestates depend on the composition of the residue, on the anaerobic reactor conditions (*i.e.*, pH, temperature, organic load, hydraulic time of residence, reactor configuration, etc.), and on the microbial community developed in the process [3,4]. Firmicutes phylum, for example, has been identified as a key group of anaerobic bacteria involved in the SCFA production. However, the predominant genera within this phylum strongly depend on the type of residue [2,5,6].

When aiming at using these SCFA in biotechnology, the wide existing biodiversity of yeasts offers many potential candidates [7]. *Yarrowia lipolytica* is generally considered a workhorse for microbial oil production and recent studies have proven its efficiency in producing high amounts of lipids from food waste-derived SCFA [8,9]. *Cutaneotrichosporon curvatum* is also a promising oleaginous yeast worth exploring for SCFA conversion given its fast growth, a very broad substrate spectrum, and high lipid accumulation capacity [10]. However, most of the studies on SCFA utilization by *C. curvatum* have been focused on the use of synthetic acetic, propionic, and butyric acids [11,12] and little information is available on its SCFA fermentation capacity from real waste-derived media. To provide more accurate information, the use of real SCFA-rich media like the one in this research work is crucial to not neglect any other compounds apart from SCFA present in the media.

Recent studies on the use of SCFA for microbial oils have identified different critical points to be considered in the process (*i.e.*, limiting SCFA concentration, SCFA profile, and C:N ratio). Furthermore, yeast growth has been reported to be hindered by SCFA concentrations higher than 5–10 g/L SCFA [13–15] and the maximum concentration of SCFA that yeasts can stand without compromising process yields still remains unknown. As a matter of fact, around 40% (w/w) lipid content in yeast cells was attained in media containing 15 g/L SCFA [16]. The inhibitory effect of SCFA does not only depend on the SCFA concentration but also on the acid distribution profile in the media. Yeasts preferably use short-chain

SCFA rather than long-chain SCFA [15–17]. It should be also highlighted that strain background also plays a key role in the potential negative effect that SCFA can exert on yeast growth and lipid production [9].

Nutrient limitation (mostly based on nitrogen) is crucial to promote lipids accumulation and repress lipid degradation pathways [17,18]. High carbon:nitrogen (C:N) ratio has been shown to favor lipid accumulation in yeast when using monosaccharides [19,20] or acetic acid as carbon sources [18,21]. However, this statement is still controversial when it comes to lipid production from other SCFA. Because organic residues often exhibit a significant nitrogen content, SCFA-rich digestates are commonly rich in ammonium [2,22]. This results in digestates exhibiting a low C:N ratio not appropriate for microbial oil production via yeast fermentation. Finding approaches to remove nitrogen that enable an appropriated C:N is thus key to increase the potential use of SCFA present in digestates as carbon sources.

In the current research work, the intrinsic ability of *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica* to efficiently produce microbial oils from the complete pool of SCFA was assessed both in synthetic and food waste (FW)-derived media. Specifically, the effects that different C:N ratios (80, 200, and 232) have on yeast growth and lipid production at high SCFA concentrations (15, 17, and 19 g/L) were evaluated. This investigation highlighted the unexpected relevance that slight variations in SCFA concentrations have on yeast lipid production. Furthermore, nitrogen removal by struvite formation was conducted in real SCFA-rich digestates evidencing the challenges associated to C:N adjustment in FW-derived media.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Yeast strains, inoculum preparation and media composition

The used strains were *C. curvatum* NRRL Y-1511 and *Y. lipolytica* ACA DC 50,109 (kindly provided by Prof George Aggelis from the Agricultural University of Athens). Both strains were maintained at 4° C on YPD agar plates (20

g/L agar, 10 g/L yeast extract, 20 g/L peptone, and 20 g/L glucose). Pre-cultures were obtained by inoculating one colony into YPD liquid medium (same composition as mentioned before but without agar) and incubating overnight in a rotary shaker at 150 rpm and 27°C. After pre-inoculum growth, cells were centrifuged and suspended in phosphate buffer solution (PBS) to the desired inoculum size for inoculating fermentation tests.

Synthetic media (SM) for fermentation experiments contained 15, 17, and 19 g/L of SCFA (detailed composition is shown in Table 1 and referred to as SM15, SM17, and SM19, respectively) and 1.70 g/L Yeast Nitrogen Base (Condalab 1553.00). SCFA concentrations and profiles were selected according to previous results [16]. Considering that concentrations higher than 15 g/L SCFA could significantly compromise cell growth and lipid production, a slight increase in the SCFA concentration to 17 g/L and 19 g/L was investigated while keeping the same SCFA profile distribution in the mixture. In order to achieve different C:N ratios (80, 200, and 232), ammonium sulfate was added taking into account the total amount of carbon present in SM15, SM17, and SM19. The resulting media were sterilized by filtration with a 0.22 µm vacuum filter.

The FW-derived medium was obtained in anaerobic fermentation processes of melon waste [2] and its composition is also shown in Table 1. Melon waste digestates were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 min (Heraeus, Megafuge 16, Thermo Scientific, Fiberlite™ F15–6 × 100y fixed-angled rotor) and filtered for sterilization and particle removal before use. Considering the total nitrogen in the digestate, the FW-derived medium had a C:N of 11.5. *Y. lipolytica* was used to ferment the real FW-derived digestates.

2.2. Struvite precipitation in FW-medium

Struvite precipitation was applied to remove ammonium nitrogen in real FW-derived medium following a method described by Liu et al., (2016) [11] with slight modifications. Specifically, Na₂HPO₄·12 H₂O was added to the FW digestate and dissolved under agitation at 200 rpm. After pH adjustment to 9.5, MgCl₂ was also added and dissolved. Na₂HPO₄·12 H₂O and MgCl₂ dosages were based on a molar ratio N:P:Mg of 1:2.6:2.6. pH was kept at 9 throughout the process. The precipitate was removed from the samples by centrifugation at 8000 g for 5 min. Total nitrogen, NH₄⁺, and SCFA were analyzed before and after the precipitation process to evaluate the nitrogen removal efficiency.

2.3. Fermentation conditions

Fermentation experiments with SM or FW-derived media were conducted in triplicates in 250-mL baffled Erlenmeyer flasks containing 100 mL of media with an initial pH of 6. Flasks were inoculated in a sterile environment with an optical density (OD) at 600 nm of 1 and incubated in a rotary shaker at 170 rpm and 27°C until more than 90% of the carbon source was consumed.

Samples were regularly withdrawn and kept at –20°C until analysis. SCFA consumption and cell growth were determined at each time point. Lipid quantification was performed at the end of the fermentation time.

2.4. Analytical methods

2.4.1. Cell growth

Cell growth was analyzed periodically by measuring the OD of the media at 600 nm (Spectroquant® Pharo 100 spectrophotometer). Dry cell biomass was determined by filtering 5 mL of sample in

Table 1. Composition of synthetic-SCFA media containing 15 g/L (SM15), 17 g/L (SM17) and 19 g/L (SM19) acids and food waste-derived medium.

	SM15	SM17	SM19	FW-derived
Acetic acid (g/L)	10.4 ± 0.1	11.6 ± 0.5	12.4 ± < 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1
Propionic acid (g/L)	0.2 ± < 0.1	0.3 ± < 0.1	0.2 ± < 0.1	0.6 ± < 0.1
Butyric acid (g/L)	2.6 ± < 0.1	2.8 ± 0.1	3.5 ± < 0.1	3.0 ± < 0.1
Valeric acid (g/L)	0.3 ± < 0.1	0.4 ± < 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.0
Hexanoic acid (g/L)	1.8 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 0.3
Total	15.2 ± 0.1	17.0 ± 0.2	18.9 ± < 0.1	11.4 ± 0.4

a pre-weighed 0.45 μm nitrocellulose filter (WhatmanTM, Buckinghamshire, UK). Filters were dried in a microwave at 170 W for 10 min and placed in a desiccator for at least 2 h. After this time, filters were weighed, and dry weight was calculated considering the weight of the cells, the weight of the filter, and the volume of the filtered sample. Biomass yield was calculated according to Equation (1).

$$Y_x : \frac{\text{Max produced biomass}(g)}{\text{Total consumed SCFA}(g)} \quad (1)$$

2.4.2. SCFA determination

Samples were filtered through a 0.22 μm membrane before analysis. SCFA and citric acid were quantified by liquid chromatography using an Agilent 1260 HPLC-RID (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with an Aminex HPX- 87 H ion exclusion column (300 $\times$ 7.8 mm I.D.) and a Cation H Refill Cartridge Microguard column (Biorad, Hercules, CA, USA). The employed mobile phase was 5 mM H_2SO_4 and isocratic elution was conducted at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. Oven and detector temperatures were 50°C and 35°C, respectively. 20 μL of samples were injected for analysis.

2.4.3. Total nitrogen, ammonium, and phosphorous determination

Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN) was determined according to Standard Methods [23] and $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ was determined using commercial test kits (ISO 000683), following the manufacturer's protocol. Phosphorous (P) was measured *via* inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (PerkinElmer, Optima 7300 DV, ICP-OES).

2.4.4. Quantification of lipids

Lipid content was fluorometrically determined with Nile Red (9-diethylamino-5 H-benzo[*a*]phenoxazine-5-one, Acros Organics) as described by Morales-Palomo and colleagues (2022) [24]. Fluorescence curves in each time point were converted to quantum yield to accurately determine lipid content. Lipid yield was calculated according to Equation (2).

$$Y_L : \frac{\text{Max produced lipids}(g)}{\text{Total consumed SCFA}(g)} \quad (2)$$

2.5. Data analysis

Statistical analyses were performed to compare the mean and standard deviation between assays. The significance of the obtained results was assessed by a one-way ANOVA considering a p-value < .05 (confidence interval 95%).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The effect of C:N ratio on yeast growth and SCFA consumption depends on SCFA concentration

Despite the high concentration of SCFA, both strains were able to grow in media containing 15, 17, and 19 g/L SCFA. As shown in Figure 1, *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica* reached the highest

Figure 1. Maximum cell biomass at the timepoint corresponding to 75–80% consumption of the carbon source. a: *C. curvatum*, b: *Y. lipolytica*. The mean difference is significant at the (*) 0.05 level.

biomass in media containing 15 g/L SCFA, regardless of the C:N used. At this SCFA concentration, there was a significant negative effect on yeast growth when increasing the C:N from 80 or 200 to 232. More specifically, 25–30% less biomass was reached with C:N 232 when compared to 80 or 200 with both yeast strains.

A different behavior was observed when the concentration of SCFA was increased from 15 g/L to 17 g/L or 19 g/L SCFA. In media containing 17 g/L and 19 g/L SCFA, the highest growth occurred at the lowest C:N ratio (C:N 80) when more nitrogen was available for the yeast with no significant differences when comparing to C:N 200 and C:N 232 independently of the yeast strain. This fact indicated that when applying restrictive conditions (in this case related to very high SCFA concentrations (*i.e.*, 17 g/L and 19 g/L SCFA)), high nitrogen availability was a crucial factor in promoting cell growth. However, if the imposed conditions are not very limiting (*i.e.* 15 g/L SCFA), yeast was capable of reaching high biomass despite the high C:N 200 (Figure 1). More specifically, *C. curvatum* (Figure 1a) and *Y. lipolytica* (Figure 1b) reached 30–40% more biomass when C:N was reduced from 200–232 to 80 in media containing both 17 g/L and 19 g/L. Thus, the positive effect of reducing C:N on cell growth was more evident when higher was the concentration of SCFA.

The promotive effect that high nitrogen availability, and subsequently low C:N, has on cell growth from SCFA was already observed in *Y. lipolytica* [16] and *C. curvatum* [12]. However, these works studied very different SCFA concentrations, and the unexpected effect that a very small increase in the SCFA concentration had on yeast response to C:N was observed in the present investigation for the first time.

Liu and colleagues [12] reported that a high amount of nitrogen channeled carbon toward cell growth. These authors observed that when acetic acid concentration increased up to inhibitory levels, the reduction of C:N was crucial to relieve the inhibition effect which was also observed in the current study at 17 g/L and 19 g/L SCFA. Strikingly, results in Figure 1 clearly indicated that low C:N is important to boost yeast cell growth when other SCFA than acetic acid are also present.

Despite the differences in cell growth (Figure 1), no differences in carbon source consumption were observed when comparing C:N 80, 200, and 232 in media containing 15 g/L (Figures 2a-d) and 17 g/L of SCFA (Figures 2b-e). Most of the 15 g/L SCFA were consumed in 52 h by *C. curvatum* (Figure 2a) and *Y. lipolytica* (Figure 2d). However, the consumed carbon source was not directed to yeast

Figure 2. SCFA consumption with *C. curvatum* (a, b, c) and *Y. lipolytica* (d, e, f) at different C:N and SCFAs initial concentrations. C:N 80 (black continuous line), C:N 200 (black dashed line), C:N 232 (grey continuous line). 15 g/L SCFA (a, d), 17 g/L SCFA (b, e), 19 g/L SCFA (c, f). Error bars ($<\pm 5\%$) are not represented due to the very good reproducibility.

growth in C:N 232, as it was the case for C:80 and C:N 200 (Figure 1). This fact resulted in a biomass yield decrease in *C. curvatum* from 0.60 g/g in the case of C:N 80 and 200 to 0.50 g/g in the case of C:N 232. In the same line, biomass yield also decreased from 0.68 g/g in C:N 80 and 200 to 0.50 g/g in C:N 232 with *Y. lipolytica*.

At 17 g/L SCFA, biomass yield in *C. curvatum* was reduced from 0.32 g/g in C:N 80 to 0.21 g/g and 0.19 g/g in C:N 200 and 232, respectively. A similar trend was observed in *Y. lipolytica* in which case, a reduction of biomass yield from 0.37 g/g to 0.23–0.25 g/g was observed when C:N increased from 80 to 200 and 232.

Contrary to what happened for 15 g/L and 17 g/L SCFA, *C. curvatum*, and *Y. lipolytica* consumed 19 g/L SCFA with higher rates at C:N 80 than at C:N 200–232 (Figure 2c-e). This fact indicated that the slight increase in SCFA concentration (2 g/L) up to a critical level (19 g/L) made nitrogen availability a key point to promote carbon source consumption, being much faster in the case of low C:N (Figure 2c-f). Biomass yields attained with *C. curvatum* from 19 g/L SCFA significantly decreased from 0.32 g/g with C:N 80 to 0.22 g/g with C:N 200–232. Accordingly, in the case of *Y. lipolytica*, these yields were 0.14, 0.18, and 0.24 g/g for C:N 80, 200, and 232, respectively.

As mentioned before, there was always a reduction of biomass yields when increasing the concentration of SCFA while maintaining the C:N. This effect agreed with previous reports dealing with *Y. lipolytica* and *C. curvatum* [25,26]. However, the significant differences of a slight increase in SCFA concentration (at the same C:N) on *Y. lipolytica* and *C. curvatum* growth yields

have been shown herein for the first time. Furthermore, the positive effect of low C:N on cell growth and carbon source consumption was demonstrated to be more pronounced at more restrictive conditions for yeasts (*i.e.*, higher concentration of SCFAs).

It is worth highlighting that at C:N 80, despite the very high SCFA concentration, *Y. lipolytica* consumed 19 g/L SCFA in 72 h (Figure 3a) while 120 h was needed to exhaust all the carbon source by *C. curvatum* (Figure 3b). In previous work, in which the performance of *Y. lipolytica* and *C. curvatum* were compared in the presence of 5, 10, and 15 g/L, the latter reached a higher biomass yield than *Y. lipolytica* in synthetic media containing 15 g/L [8]. Nevertheless, in this previous study, SCFA profile was significantly different and media contained much less acetic acid in the SCFA pool than in the current study (4.9 g/L vs 10.4 g/L). It could be thus concluded that different SCFA profiles and ratios in the media influenced the carbon source consumption rates of specific acids, determining biomass yields and subsequently product titers.

As shown in Figure 3, in media containing 19 g/L SCFA and C:N 80, *Y. lipolytica* consumed 96% of the acetic acid in less than 60 h and at the same time point, only 56% of this acid was consumed by *C. curvatum*. One of the most significant differences when comparing acid consumption profiles was the clear co-consumption of propionic acid and acetic acid in the case of *Y. lipolytica* (Figure 3a). By contrast, *C. curvatum* started to metabolize propionic acid only when 50% of the acetic acid was consumed (Figure 3b). This effect has not been previously identified in *C. curvatum*

Figure 3. Acetic (•), propionic (□), butyric (■), valeric (○), and hexanoic acid (◆) consumption in media containing 19 g/L SCFA and C:N 80. *Y. lipolytica* (a). *C. curvatum* (b). Error bars ($<\pm 5\%$) are not represented due to the very good reproducibility.

and indicated that different yeast strains may have different acid preferences and requirements when SCFAs are found in a mixture. Thus, both SCFA concentration and profile have to be considered to select a suitable yeast strain for microbial oils production from SCFA.

3.2. Lipid production at different SCFA concentrations and C:N ratios

Figure 4 shows an increase in lipid content in *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica* when SCFA concentration increased from 15 g/L to 17 g/L and 19 g/L. At 15 g/L SCFA, lipid content increased from $12.0 \pm 0.8\%$ (w/w) to $34.0 \pm 1.7\%$ (w/w) and from $19.6 \pm 0.6\%$ (w/w) to $41.6 \pm 0.5\%$ when C:N increased from 80 to 200 for both *C. curvatum* and *Y. lipolytica*, respectively. However, contrary to what was expected, a further increase in C:N from 200 to 232 did not result in an increase in lipid content but a significant decrease was shown. As previously discussed, in fermentations with 15 g/L SCFA, an increase in C:N from 80–200 to 232 resulted in lower cell biomass (Figure 1). The reason for this behavior lies in the production of

Figure 4. Lipid content % (w/w) in *C. curvatum* (a) and *Y. lipolytica* (b) from different SCFA-rich synthetic media and different C:N. The mean difference is significant at the (*) 0.05 level.

secondary metabolites that may act as protectors under stressful conditions [27]. With a reduced growth (due to an excessively high C:N), citric acid cannot be totally cleaved by ATP-citrate lyase inside the cell and its excess is secreted out of the cell leading to an important reduction in lipids production [13]. In this study, independently of the SCFA concentration, *Y. lipolytica* excreted 1.5 g/L citric acid at the end of fermentation with C:N 80 and 6 g/L with C:N 200–230 (data not shown). In the same line, *C. curvatum* excreted 2 g/L citric acid with C:N 80 and 5.3 g/L with C:N 200–230 (data not shown). Those results proved that citric acid was released in the media at high C:N (*i.e.*, low biomass yields).

The evident negative effect that an excessively high C:N exerted on lipid production from 15 g/L SCFA was not observed when using 17 g/L and 19 g/L SCFA. More concretely, lipid content in *C. curvatum* grown in 19 g/L SCFA, significantly increased from $41.7 \pm 3.9\%$ (w/w) at C:N 80 to $51.3 \pm 3.4\%$ (w/w) and $57.2 \pm 1.6\%$ (w/w) with C:N 200 and 232, respectively. Additionally, no significant differences were observed in lipid content with *Y. lipolytica* at 19 g/L SCFA, reaching a lipid content as high as $78.4 \pm 0.6\%$ (w/w). It should be highlighted at this point that those values were among the highest lipid contents reported on wild-type strains using SCFA as carbon sources. These results suggested that the challenging conditions imposed by high SCFA concentrations promoted that part of the carbon source was diverted for lipid production instead of growth. Furthermore, results indicated that at high SCFA concentration, the effect that different C:N had on cell growth and lipid production was specie-specific and could depend on the inherent robustness of the yeast.

3.3. Lipid production from FW-derived media after C:N adjustment by struvite precipitation

Owing to the higher lipid content obtained in *Y. lipolytica* when compared with *C. curvatum*, *Y. lipolytica* was selected for lipid production from real FW-derived media. Considering the very high amount of nitrogen in the media, ammonium was removed via struvite precipitation subsequently increasing C:N. In the struvite

treatment, total nitrogen and NH_4^+ were reduced from 720 mg/L and 444 mg/L to 68 mg/L and 32.4 mg/L, respectively. These results proved that 90% of the nitrogen was removed from the soluble fraction of the effluent. These values were in the range previously reported for the removal of nitrogen using effluents collected from the anaerobic digestates [11]. Nitrogen removal resulted in an increase in C:N up to 115. After struvite precipitation, phosphorous was also reduced from 232 mg/L to 115 mg/L.

As shown in Figure 5a, SCFA concentration was not affected during precipitation, and both, treated and non-treated media had the same initial SCFA concentration. However, as it was previously shown in fermentation tests with synthetic media, the reduction in nitrogen content and the concomitant increase in C:N lowered the cell growth from 12.4 ± 0.4 g/L to 9.4 ± 0.4 g/L (Figure 5a). Lipid content in *Y. lipolytica* also increased from $17.9 \pm 3.9\%$ (w/w) to $41.9 \pm 2.6\%$ (w/w) when FW-media was subjected to struvite precipitation (Figure 5b). This 2.4-fold increase indicated again that the consumed carbon was directed to lipid production instead of growth and showed the effect that high C:N exhibited on promoting lipid accumulation. Considering cell growth and produced lipids, lipid yields were 0.36 g/g in struvite-treated media and 0.20 g/g in non-treated media. The lipid yield obtained in treated media was similar to that previously obtained with the same yeast strain in FW SCFA-rich digestates with a much higher presence of acetic acid (*i.e.* the

preferred SCFA for *Y. lipolytica*) [16]. Remarkably, these yields were also significantly higher than those achieved by *Y. lipolytica* from microalgae digestates containing 5–15 g/L SCFA (0.05–0.08 g/g) [8] and from FW-digestates in two-stage batch cultures (0.15 g/g) [28].

These results proved that struvite precipitation was an effective method to remove nitrogen from FW-derived media. Agreeing with previous reports in which hydrodynamic cavitation was applied as pretreatment of livestock wastewater [29], struvite formation resulted in a marked decrease in phosphorous (50% removal). This phosphorous removal also gave rise to an increase in C:P ratio that has been recently proven to be a promising strategy for improve lipid production [30,31]. Yeast was not affected by any other potential by-products released in the treatment and no additional clearance steps would be required for its application.

4. Conclusions

Low C:N can alleviate the inhibitory effect that restrictive conditions associated with high SCFA concentration exert on yeast growth. By contrast, high C:N promoted that part of the carbon source was diverted to lipid production instead of growth at very high SCFA concentration (19 g/L). Unexpectedly, a slight increase in SCFA concentration provoked significant differences in yeast performance. Acids distribution profile in the media has to be considered when selecting

Figure 5. (a) *Y. lipolytica* growth (◆) and SCFAs consumption (●) in real FW-derived media without struvite precipitation (dashed line) and with struvite precipitation (solid line); (b) lipid content in *Y. lipolytica* produced from SCFAs in non-precipitated FW-digestate (light grey) and precipitated FW-digestate (dark grey).

appropriate yeast strains since they may have diverse acid preferences and differently metabolize acids when present in a mixture. In the same line, the effect that different C:N exhibited on cell growth and lipid production was specie-specific and could depend on the inherent robustness of the yeast.

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Disclosure statement

Authors do not have interests to declare

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Authors contributions

Elia Tomás-Pejó, Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Review & Editing, Supervision, Sergio Morales-Palomo Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing, Cristina González-Fernández Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, ETP, upon reasonable request.

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